

ROAD SAFETY MANAGEMENT CAPACITY ASSESSMENT IN NORTH MACEDONIA

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Abstract

Road safety management capacity is critical for reducing traffic accidents and associated fatalities. Despite ongoing efforts to improve road safety, North Macedonia continues to experience higher rates of road traffic crashes compared to EU averages. This study aims to assess existing road safety management capacities in North Macedonia by identifying strengths and weaknesses in order to inform policy interventions and institutional improvements. The assessment is conducted using a structured questionnaire adapted from international guidelines and administered to national and local stakeholders involved in road safety.

The study identifies gaps in strategic planning, institutional coordination, data management systems, and human resource capacities within North Macedonia's road safety management framework. Strengthening road safety management requires targeted interventions, including enhanced inter-agency coordination, improving data collection and analysis systems, and the development of sustainable funding mechanisms. Building local-level capacity through structured training programs and institutional reforms is essential for the effective implementation of road safety policies. This research provides a foundational analysis to support policymakers in formulating evidence-based strategies aimed at significantly reducing traffic accidents and fatalities.

Keywords: road safety, traffic accidents, capacity assessment, management

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Official statistical data from the World Health Organization (WHO) indicate that approximately 1.19 million people die annually in road traffic crashes, while nearly 50 million are injured. A staggering 92% of all fatalities occur in low- and middle- income countries. Road traffic injuries remain the leading cause of death among children and young people aged 5–29 years (WHO, 2023).

The Stockholm Declaration affirmed the vital role of road safety in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals and called upon the United Nations to set an ambitious target to reduce global road traffic deaths and serious injuries by 50% by 2030 (El-Adawy et al., 2022). In Europe, road safety policy has been guided by the Safe System and Vision Zero approach, with intermediate targets aimed at halving the number of fatalities and, for the first time, the number of seriously injured persons by 2030, as a step toward achieving near-zero deaths by 2050.

In line with European objective, one of the main goals of the National Transport Strategy of North Macedonia is to reduce the number of road traffic fatalities by 50% by 2030 compared to 2017 (MoTC, 2018). Although initial progress toward this target exceeded expectations, with a 25.2% reduction recorded in 2021, a reversal occurred in 2022. Over the past three years, an increasing trend of 22.4% has been observed (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Number of fatalities per year²⁴

Over the past 15 years, an average of 144 people per year have been killed on roads in North Macedonia. In 2024 alone, road traffic crashes resulted in 142 fatalities and 1,085 serious injuries. The fatality rate, expressed as the number of deaths per million inhabitants, stands at 67, significantly higher than the European Union average of 46 fatalities per million inhabitants (Figure 2).

²⁴ Ministry of Interior.

Figure 2: Fatality rate – fatalities/million inhabitants²⁵

Road traffic crashes represent not only a major public health issue but also a significant socio-economic challenge, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (Pavleski & Jolakoski, 2025). Beyond the toll on victims and their families, traffic crashes impose substantial economic costs. According to World Bank, the costs of road traffic crashes in North Macedonia amounts to approximately 2.1% of GDP (Jovanov, Kukuc, et al., 2023), equivalent to roughly €300 million annually.

Road safety management capacities refer to the readiness and ability of public authorities to implement necessary measures and activities efficiently and in a timely manner, and to achieve policy, regulatory, and practice changes required to manage the road transport system effectively and deliver improved safety outcomes (Breen et al., 2018).

The subject of the research is the assessment of road safety management capacities, while the objective is to analyze current institutional practices related to road traffic safety and to identify opportunities for strengthening coordination and efficiency at both national and local levels, in line with international best practices.

1.2. Road Safety Management System

The road safety management system can be conceptualized as consisting of three interrelated elements: institutional management functions, interventions and results (Figure 3). Managing for road safety outcomes requires an integrated and accountable response across all these elements of the system. This conceptual framework is derived from New Zealand’s comprehensive road safety target-setting model, introduced in 2010, which linked desired safety outcomes with interventions and institutional implementation arrangements (Bliss & Breen, 2013; Breen et al., 2008).

The road safety management system possesses several generic characteristics that enable its application across countries regardless of development level or road safety performance. It emphasizes that road safety outcomes are “produced” in the same manner as other public goods and services. The production process is conceptualized as a

²⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>

management system operating at three levels: institutional management functions generate interventions, which in turn produce results. The model is neutral with respect to country-specific governance structures and cultural context, which shape how institutions operate and how goals are set and achieved (Bliss & Breen, 2013; SafetyNet, 2009).

Figure 3: Road Safety Management System (Martensen et al., 2021)

2.1.1. Institutional management functions

A focus on results constitutes the core institutional management function for achieving improved road safety results. All other institutional management functions are subordinate to this overarching focus and contribute to its realization. A country's results focus reflects a pragmatic articulation of its ambition to improve road safety, along with the means agreed upon to achieve that ambition. In the absence of a clear and accountable focus on results, institutional functions and interventions lack cohesion, thereby undermining the efficiency and effectiveness of safety initiatives (Bliss & Breen, 2013; Breen et al., 2008).

Coordination refers to the alignment and orchestration of interventions and related institutional management functions delivered by government entities in cooperation with community and business partners to achieve the desired safety outcomes.

Legislation encompasses the legal instruments required for governance, defining institutional mandates, responsibilities, accountability mechanisms and interventions necessary to achieve the desired focus on results.

Funding and resource allocation concerns the sustainable financing of interventions and institutional management functions through rational evaluation and programming frameworks.

Promotion involves sustained communication of road safety as a core responsibility for government and society and emphasizes shared societal accountability to support the delivery of the interventions required.

Monitoring and evaluation entail the systematic and ongoing measurement of road safety outputs and outcomes (intermediate and final), as well as and the evaluation of interventions.

Research and development, along with knowledge transfer, involve the systematic and continuous generation, codification, dissemination and application of knowledge to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of the road safety management system.

2.1.2. Interventions

Interventions are designed to achieve the defined results focus. They address the safe planning, design and operation, and use of the road network, the conditions under which vehicles and road users interact with the system, and the effective recovery and rehabilitation of crash victims. Interventions also establish standards and rules intended to secure compliance and enhance overall safety (Bliss & Breen, 2013; Breen et al., 2008).

2.1.3. Results

The final component of the road safety management system concerns the measurement of outcomes and formulation of targets expressed in terms of final outcomes, intermediate outcomes, and outputs. Targets articulate the desired level of safety performance endorsed by governments, stakeholders and the community. Countries demonstrating good practice typically adopt quantitative outcome and intermediate targets, supplemented by output targets aligned with these objectives. (Bliss & Breen, 2013; Breen et al., 2008).

2. METHODOLOGY

2.2. Assessment framework

The review of road safety management capacities in the Republic of North Macedonia is based on the assessment framework defined in the *Guidelines for Road Safety Management Capacity Reviews and Safe System Projects* of the Global Road Safety Facility (GRSF) under the World Bank. The assessment framework consists of a series of checklists with structured questions based on identified good practices in road safety management (Bliss & Breen, 2013; Jovanov, Pavleski, et al., 2023). These checklists enable a detailed examination of all elements of the road safety management system and their relationship with current practices (Figure 4).

Checklist 1: Lead agency role and institutional management functions				
Questions	Yes	Partial	Pending	No
Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the results focus management functions? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Appraising current road safety performance through high-level strategic review? Adopting a far-reaching road safety vision for the longer term? Analyzing what could be achieved in the medium term? Setting quantitative targets by mutual consent across the road safety partnership? Establishing mechanisms to ensure partnership accountability for results? 				
Checklist 1: Results focus at system level				
Does the lead coordinator? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Horiz Vertic Specif and b Partic 				
Are estimates of the social costs of crashes available?				
Does the lead legislation? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revis Devel Cons Socia 				
Are data on road deaths and injuries readily available?				
Have the risks faced by road users been identified? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drivers? Passengers? Motorcyclists? Cyclists? Children? Others? 				
Does the lead funding en? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensur Estab prog 				
Checklist 2: Planning, design, operation and use of the road network				
Has a nation term be? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Have national Soc Prom Chan Multi Inte Lead Devel Identif to achie Carry Hig Pol Pla 				
Have comprehensive safety standards and rules and associated performance targets been set for the planning, design, operation and use of roads to achieve the desired focus on results? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> National roads? Regional roads? Provincial roads? City roads? 				
Are the official speed limits aligned with Safe-System design principles to achieve the desired focus on results? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> National roads? Regional roads? Provincial roads? City roads? 				
For each category of roads (national, regional, provincial, city) are compliance regimes in place to ensure adherence to specified safety standards and rules to achieve the desired focus on results? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Road safety impact assessment? Road safety audit? Road safety inspection? Black spot management? Network safety management? Speed management? Alcohol management? Safety belts management? Helmets management? Fatigue management? 				
Do the specified safety standards and rules and related compliance regimes clearly address the safety priorities of high-risk road user groups to achieve the desired focus on results?				
Is the lead ag annual pe?				
Do the specified safety standards and rules and related compliance regimes compare favorably with international good practices?				

Figure 4: Example of checklists

The elements of the assessment framework include:

- Key institutional management functions (focus on results, coordination, legislation, financing and resource allocation, promotion, monitoring and evaluation, research and development, and knowledge transfer), which provide the foundation for:
- Multisectoral, system-wide interventions (safe roads, safe speeds, safe vehicles, safe users, and post-crash care), aimed at achieving:
- Results, including the costs of road crashes, crash outcome indicators, road safety performance indicators, and process indicators.

Checklist findings must be interpreted using expert road safety management judgment. If responses to the questions are predominantly “no” or “pending”, national capacity is considered weak. A high number of “pending” or “partial” responses also indicate weak capacity, although signs of capacity strengthening may be evident and should be acknowledged and encouraged. Capacity can be considered strong only when there is a predominance of “yes” responses. It is important to reach consensus on the assessment for each element of the road safety management system being appraised (Bliss & Breen, 2013).

2.3. Implementation steps

2.3.1. Set review objectives

The generic objectives of a country road safety management capacity review are to:

- Establish an integrated multisectoral framework for dialogue with country partners and stakeholders on potential road safety investments;
- Assess government ownership of road safety results and identify related institutional responsibilities and accountabilities;

- Reach official consensus on road safety management capacity weaknesses and institutional strengthening and investment priorities to address them;
- Identify Safe System implementation projects to support the investment strategy.
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2.3.2. Prepare for review

Careful preparation for a country road safety management review is critical to its overall success. High-level national commitment to the review must be ensured; otherwise, the review objectives cannot be achieved. The review should be conducted by experienced, internationally recognized road safety experts with senior management experience at both national and international levels.

An inception report should be prepared by the client country prior to the review to outline the basic elements of the road safety management system and to provide available data on road safety results and trends. A detailed consultation schedule should be prepared in advance and managed locally to ensure a smooth flow of meetings, with flexibility to reschedule where necessary if the availability of key officials changes (Bliss & Breen, 2013).

2.3.3. Appraise results focus at system level

The road safety management system provides the framework for conducting a country road safety management capacity review. The checklist for appraising results focus at the system level addresses the following questions (Bliss & Breen, 2013):

- Are estimates of the social costs of road crashes available?
- Are data on road traffic deaths and injuries readily available?
- Have the risks faced by road users been systematically identified?
- Has a national long-term vision for improved road safety performance been officially adopted?
- Have national and regional targets for improved safety performance been established?
- Have all agencies responsible for improved safety performance been identified and formally held accountable for achieving the desired results?
- Have the responsibilities of industry, community and business stakeholders for improved road safety performance reviews been clearly defined?
- Are regular performance reviews conducted to assess progress and implement improvements?
- Has a lead agency been formally established to direct the national road safety effort?
- Is the role of the lead agency defined in legislation, policy documents, or annual performance agreements?

2.3.4. Appraise results focus at interventions level

Following the appraisal of results focus at the system level, capacity must be assessed in terms of results focus at the interventions level. Interventions address the safe planning, design, operation and use of the road network; the conditions under which vehicles and road users can safely operate; and the recovery and rehabilitation of crash victims. They also establish specific standards and rules aimed at achieving this safety and ensuring compliance.

The assessment considers three broad categories of interventions and examines the linkages between interventions, their outputs, intermediate outcomes, and final outcomes.

The following checklists define the scope of appraisal at the intervention level (Bliss & Breen, 2013).

Planning, design, operation, and use of the road network:

- Have comprehensive safety standards, rules, and performance targets been established for road planning, design, operation and use?
- Are official speed limits aligned with Safe System design principles?
- For each road category (national, regional, provincial, urban), are compliance regimes in place to ensure adherence to safety standards?
- Do safety standards and rules and compliance regimes address the priorities of high-risk road user groups?
- Do these standards and rules and compliance regimes compare favorably with international good practice?

Entry and exit of vehicles to and from the road network:

- Have comprehensive safety standards, rules, and associated performance targets been established to regulate vehicle entry and exit?
- For each vehicle and safety equipment category (private, commercial, public transport, helmets), are compliance regimes in place?
- Do these safety standards and compliance regimes address the priorities of high-risk road user groups?
- Do they compare favorably with international good practice?

Entry and exit of road users to and from the road network:

- Have comprehensive safety standards, rules, and performance targets been established for road users entry and exit?
- For each driver category (private, commercial, public), are compliance regimes in place?
- Do these standards and compliance regimes address the priorities of high-risk road user groups?
- Do they compare favorably with international good practice?
- Have comprehensive safety standards and performance targets been established for the recovery and rehabilitation of crash victims?
- For each category of post-crash care (pre-hospital, hospital, long term care), are compliance regimes in place?
- Do post-crash care standards and compliance regimes adequately address the needs of high-risk road user groups?

2.3.5. Appraise results focus at the institutional management functions level

It is important to examine each institutional management function and explore its linkages with the identified interventions and their intended results focus. The following checklists set out the appraisal framework that addresses the crucial contribution of institutional management functions subordinate to the desired focus on results (Bliss & Breen, 2013).

The checklist for Coordination covers the following questions:

- Are interventions coordinated horizontally across agencies to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Are interventions coordinated vertically between national, regional, provincial and city agencies to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Have robust intervention delivery partnerships between agencies, industry, communities and the business sector been established to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Have parliamentary committees and procedures supporting the coordination process been established to achieve the desired focus on results?

The checklist for Legislation covers the following questions:

- Are legislative instruments and procedures supporting interventions and institutional management functions sufficient to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Are legislative instruments and procedures supporting interventions and institutional management functions regularly reviewed and reformed to achieve the desired focus on results?

The checklist for Funding and resource allocation covers the following questions:

- Are sustainable funding mechanisms supporting interventions and institutional management functions in place to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Are formal resource allocation procedures supporting interventions and institutional management functions in place to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Is there an official Value of a Statistical Life and related values for injuries to guide resource allocation decisions?
- Are funding mechanisms and resource allocation procedures supporting interventions and institutional management functions sufficient to achieve the desired focus on results?

The checklist for Promotion covers the following questions:

- Is road safety regularly promoted to achieve the desired focus on results?

The checklist for Monitoring and evaluation covers the following questions:

- For each category of roads (national, regional, provincial, urban) are sustainable systems in place to collect and manage data on road crashes, fatality and injury outcomes, and all related road environment/vehicle/road user factors to achieve the desired focus on results?
- For each category of roads (national, regional, provincial, urban) are sustainable systems in place to collect and manage data on road network traffic, vehicle speeds, safety belt and helmet wearing rates to achieve the desired focus on results?
- For each category of roads (national, regional, provincial, urban) are regular safety rating surveys undertaken to quality assure adherence to specified safety standards and rules, to achieve the desired focus on results?

- For each category of roads (national, regional, provincial, urban) are systems in place to collect and manage data on the output quantities and qualities of safety interventions implemented to achieve the desired focus on results?
- For each category of vehicles and safety equipment (private, commercial, public transport, helmets) are systematic and regular safety rating surveys undertaken to quality assure adherence to the specified safety standards and rules to achieve the desired focus on results?
- For each category of post-crash care (pre-hospital, hospital, long-term care) are systematic and regular surveys undertaken to quality assure adherence to the specified standards and rules to achieve the desired focus on result?
- Are systems in place to regularly monitor and evaluate safety performance against established targets to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Do all participating agencies and external partners and stakeholders have open access to all collected data?

The checklist for Research and development and knowledge transfer covers the following questions:

- Has a national road safety research and development strategy been established to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Has an independent national road safety research organization been established to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Have demonstration and pilot programs been conducted to achieve the desired focus on results?
- Are mechanisms and communication channels in place to disseminate the findings of national road safety research and development to achieve the desired focus on results?

2.3.6. Assess lead agency role and identify capacity strengthening priorities

In good-practice countries, the lead agency (or the informal lead agency/agencies) plays a preeminent role in most institutional management functions, although in some cases it may adopt more of a guiding, facilitating or catalytic role. The lead agency assumes responsibility within government for developing the national road safety strategy and defining its results focus, which represents the overarching institutional management function.

The checklist for assessing the lead agency role covers the following questions (Bliss & Breen, 2013):

- Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the results focus management function?
- Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the coordination management function?
- Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the legislation management function?
- Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the funding and resource allocation management function?
- Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the promotion management function?

- Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the monitoring and evaluation management function?
- Does the lead agency (or de facto lead agency/agencies) effectively contribute to the research and development and knowledge transfer management function?

2.3.7. Specify investment strategy and identify Safe System implementation projects

This stage of the capacity review addresses the specification of a long-term investment strategy aimed at accelerating the transition from a low-capacity to a high-capacity road safety management system and identifying appropriate implementation options. Safety management capacity weaknesses in low- and middle-income countries present a formidable barrier to progress and typically require strengthening of institutional management functions. Similar capacity gaps may also arise in high-income countries as their results focus shifts towards higher levels of ambition.

In both contexts, an investment strategy must be designed to overcome inherent capacity weaknesses by first establishing a core institutional capacity to bring safety outcomes under control, then scaling up investment to accelerate capacity building across the entire road network, and finally consolidating these gains on a sustainable basis (Bliss & Breen, 2013).

2.3.8. Confirm review findings at high-level workshop

A workshop should be planned and scheduled as a formal component of the capacity review process, with the objective of confirming and integrating the findings derived from the checklists and addressing any unresolved or previously unidentified issues. The workshop should bring together all relevant stakeholders in a multisectoral setting that enables comprehensive discussion of all elements of the road safety management system, fostering a spirit of strategic partnership and shared responsibility for improving road safety outcomes (Bliss & Breen, 2013).

2.3.9. Finalize review report

A draft report presenting the capacity review findings should be circulated during the final phase of the review to all participants and relevant government bodies for comments and validation. Following incorporation of feedback, a final report should be prepared and formally distributed (Bliss & Breen, 2013).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Implementation of the road safety management capacity review in North Macedonia

The successful implementation of the Road Safety Management Capacity Review required the active involvement of all relevant stakeholders to assess existing road safety management capacities and practices and to reach consensus on identified weaknesses across the entire system. To facilitate the review process, a Steering Committee was established, comprising representatives from key institutions and organizations, including the Ministry of Transport, Ministry of Interior, Ministry of Economy and Labour, Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Education and Science, Ministry of Health, the Republic Council for Road Traffic Safety, and the Association of Local Self-Government Units.

In addition to these core stakeholders, the consultation process engaged representatives from central and local government, academia, civil society organizations, the professional sector, and international organizations (Jovanov, Kukuc, et al., 2023).

To discuss the findings and recommendations, a workshop was organized at the level of state secretaries and institutional directors. The consultation process concluded with a high-level final workshop, aimed at validating the findings and recommendations and addressing any issues not previously identified during the review. This workshop also served to achieve official consensus on strengthening road safety management capacities and to clarify institutional responsibilities, particularly concerning the role of the lead road safety agency and the enhancement of management capacities.

The revised final draft report of the Road Safety Management Capacity Review, including the Investment Strategy and Action Plan, was shared with all stakeholders for final written comments and feedback. The Action Plan outlines an expanded set of activities addressing key weaknesses identified during the review process. These activities are envisaged as project components within the broader Safe System framework and are fully aligned with the EU approach and the next generation of road safety strategies. The Action Plan is structured around six intervention areas: Road Safety Management, Safe Roads and Mobility, Safe Vehicles, Safe Road Users, Post-Crash Care, and Safe Speeds (Jovanov, Kukuc, et al., 2023). In total, the Action Plan defines 40 activities distributed across these intervention areas.

3.2. Key findings and recommendations

The review indicates that although the number of road traffic fatalities and serious injuries has declined, these figures continue to fluctuate over time, underscoring the need to strengthen coordination and adopt a more systematic and integrated approach. While the country has implemented certain initial measures and achieved several “low-hanging fruit” outcomes, sustaining and accelerating these positive trends requires the full establishment of a Safe System approach.

A strong need exists to introduce a data-driven road safety management framework. Beyond monitoring final outcomes such as crash numbers and consequences, the introduction of key performance indicators (KPIs) is essential to enable targeted interventions focused on high-risk road user behaviors (Jovanov, Kukuc, et al., 2023).

The key recommendations for advancing road safety in North Macedonia include:

- Development of a national road safety strategy, action plan, and annual implementation programs
- Alignment of the existing road crash database with the CADaS protocol and establishment of data exchange with the EU CARE database
- Establishment of a national integrated road safety database
- Proactive monitoring of road safety through indirect performance indicators
- Assessment of the socio-economic impacts of road traffic crashes
- Implementation of self-explaining and forgiving road design principles in accordance with the Safe System Approach
- Application of safe speed principles in road design
- Implementation of road infrastructure safety management procedures (RSIA, RSA, RSI, Risk Mapping, NSM, IDS)
- Establishment of a central vehicle registry
- Deployment of an automated traffic enforcement system

- Introduction of the MAIS3+ injury severity scale and improved data exchange between health institutions and the police
- Strengthening road safety education within formal education systems
- Enhancement of driver training programs and introduction of a graduated driver licensing system
- Continued efforts to establish a Road Traffic Safety Agency
- Activation of the National Coordinating Body for Road Safety Improvement
- Harmonization of national legislation with EU road safety directives and regulations
- Adoption of a sustainable financing model for road safety and improved resource allocation
- Full adoption of the Safe System Approach

CONCLUSION

The review of road safety management capacities in North Macedonia identified both the current institutional landscape and relevant international best practices, providing recommendations at systemic, operational, and institutional levels. Institutional capacities remain limited and require improved coordination, stable financing, and stronger accountability mechanisms. Achieving a sustained reduction in fatalities and serious injuries necessitates organized, systematic, and data-driven action, supported by the full implementation of the Safe System Approach.

The effective implementation of World Report recommendations requires a comprehensive and long-term commitment, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where the process may span a decade or more. Countries must first assess their road safety management capacity and readiness to undertake sustained reforms and investments. The assessment framework provides diagnostic tools to identify underlying conditions that influence success or failure and ensures that interventions are properly sequenced and aligned with institutional absorptive capacity. However, successful implementation requires the involvement of experienced road safety specialists with proven strategic management expertise at national and international levels.

Although each country faces unique challenges, experience from high-income countries demonstrates that effective road safety management is inherently complex. The sophistication of institutional arrangements in such contexts can be viewed as a proxy for success and sustained commitment to road safety investment. Ultimately, the implementation of World Report recommendations must be grounded in practice through a “learning by doing” approach, supported by targeted investments aimed at overcoming institutional capacity constraints

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